

CAVITATION AND FRACTURE IN HIGH STRAIN RATE SUPERPLASTIC $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{AL}$ COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Tensile tests have been carried out under a constant stress condition at 833 K and the level and characteristics of cavitation resulting from tensile superplastic flow have been examined using metallographic and densitometric techniques in a high strain rate superplastic $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Al-Mg-Si}$ composite. Cavities were nucleated preferentially at the matrix/reinforcement interfaces. The cavity volume depended on the applied stress and the strain. The rates of an increase in the cavity volume as a function of strain were much lower for the composite than for a superplastic 7475 alloy.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites with ceramic reinforcements exhibit a unique combination of high specific room temperature strength and modulus, and therefore the composites show promise as structural materials. However, the composites have lower tensile ductility than the matrix alloys. This gives rise to high costs in the final forming of the composites. It is therefore desirable to improve tensile ductility of the composites for many structural applications.

It has been demonstrated that many aluminum matrix composites with discontinuous reinforcements behaved in a superplastic-like manner [1-9]. These results indicate a possibility of superplastic forming of the composites. Nieh *et al.* [1] showed that a $\text{SiC}_w/\text{Al-Cu-Mg}$ composite exhibited superplastic behavior at a high strain rate of $3.3 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Recently it was reported that $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Al}$ composites showed superplasticity at high strain rates ($> 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) [4,6,8,9]. High strain rate superplasticity is attractive for commercial applications because one of major problems in current superplastic forming technique is very slow forming rates of typically 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} s^{-1} .

The mechanisms of high strain rate superplasticity in the composites are currently the subject of some debate. It is recognized that a high value of the strain rate sensitivity, m , is responsible for superplastic deformation for metals. High m is clearly associated with superplastic deformation of the composites as well because high values of m are attained for superplastic composites. However it is of interest to note that the optimum strain rate for the largest elongation does not coincide with the strain rate for the maximum m for superplastic composites [6,7]. This discrepancy is likely associated with cavitation behavior [10]. It is important to investigate characteristics of cavitation since it is recognized that excessive cavitation may impose significant limitation on the commercial use of superplastically-formed components. There are a few of studies on cavitation in high strain rate superplastic composites [10-12], however, there

are too few data to understand characteristics and mechanisms of cavitation in high strain rate superplastic composites. In this work, tensile tests have been carried out under a constant stress condition at 833 K and the level and characteristics of cavitation resulting from tensile superplastic flow have been examined using metallographic and densitometric techniques in a high strain rate superplastic $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Al-Mg-Si}$ composite. Measurements of cavities under a constant stress condition are suitable for exact cavitation investigations because important parameters for cavitation characteristics: the critical cavity size, the rate of cavity growth and so on, depend on the stress.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Commercial powder of Al-Mg-Si (6061) alloy of less than 20 μm in diameter was supplied by Toyo Aluminum Ltd., and Si_3N_4 particulate of less than 0.5 μm in diameter was supplied by UBE Industries Ltd. Both powders of the aluminum alloy and the Si_3N_4 particulates were ultrasonically mixed in an alcoholic solvent followed by drying. The mixed powders were sintered at 873 K for 1.2 ks at a pressure of 390 MPa. The sintered billet was then extruded at 773 K with a ratio of 100 : 1. The grain size of the extruded composite was 1.9 μm .

Tensile specimens were machined from the final extruded bar. The specimens had a gage length of 4.5 mm and a gage diameter of 2.5 mm. Constant true stress tensile tests were carried out from 4 to 12 MPa with 833 K in air. The testing temperature of 833 K is slightly above the partial melting point of the composite (829 K). The tensile axis was selected to be parallel to the extrusion direction for all tests. The strain rate at a given applied stress was determined at $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.1$, where ϵ is the strain.

To examine cavitation using density measurements and metallographs, specimens were strained to preselected elongations short of failure. The volume of cavities was determined by hydrostatic weighing in water with a corresponding gauge head being used as a density standard. Both the gauge length and the gauge head were mechanically polished with a fine abrasive paper prior to density measurement. Metallographic studies of cavities were carried out using high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) of HITACHI S-900.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SUPERPLASTIC BEHAVIOR

The variation in the strain rate (top) and the elongation to failure (bottom) as a function of the applied stress is shown in Fig. 1. The strain rate at elevated temperature for crystalline materials may be given by

$$\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, σ is the flow stress and n is the stress exponent, which is the reciprocal of m . It is recognized that for superplastic deformation, low n or high m (> 0.3) is responsible for stability of plastic deformation, resulting in large elongations. The low stress exponent of $n=2$ or the high strain rate sensitivity of $m=0.5$ was attained in a stress range from 6 to 12 MPa. The range is considered to be a superplastic region because of high m . The strain rates in the superplastic region are $1 \sim 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which are much higher than conventional superplastic strain rates of typically 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} s^{-1} .

Large elongations to failure of more than 400 % were attained in a stress range from 6 to 10 MPa. However, the elongation to failure decreased rapidly at higher stresses of more than 11 MPa. It should be noted that the elongation to failure strongly depended on the applied stress even in the region of the same stress exponent of 2. The specimens deformed to failure at the given applied stresses with 833 K are shown in Fig. 2. Significant development of necking was found in the specimen deformed at 4 MPa. The lower elongation at 4 MPa is likely attributed to development of necking. However, significant development of necking was not found in the specimen deformed at 12 MPa. Development of necking is not responsible for a rapid decrease in the elongation to failure at higher stresses of more than 11 MPa. Hence stress dependence of the elongation to failure can not be interpreted only by instability of plastic deformation.

Fig. 1 The variation in the strain rate (top) and the elongation to failure (bottom) at 833 K as a function of the applied stress.

Fig. 2 The specimens deformed to failure at various applied stresses with 833 K.

CAVITATION

Cavity nucleation was investigated by HRSEM. The micrographs of the specimens deformed to $\epsilon = 0.7$ at 8 and 12 MPa with 833 K are shown in Fig. 3. Cavities were nucleated preferentially at the matrix/reinforcement interfaces for both specimens. Most of cavities were

8 MPa

12 MPa

Fig. 3 Micrographs of the specimens deformed to $\epsilon = 0.7$ at 8 and 12 MPa with 833 K.

very small ($\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) and large cavities ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$) were not found. The number of the cavities at 12 MPa was larger than that at 8 MPa. The critical cavity radius which will be stable under an applied tensile stress σ is given by

$$r_c = 2\gamma_s/\sigma \quad (2)$$

where r_c is the critical cavity radius and γ_s is the surface energy. It is expected from eqn. (2) that the critical cavity radius decreases with increasing stress. Therefore the result that the number of cavities at 12 MPa was larger than that at 8 MPa is likely because of the difference in the critical cavity radius.

Large cavities of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ were observed in the specimens deformed to $\epsilon = 1.8$ at 8 MPa and $\epsilon = 1.3$ at 12 MPa (Fig. 4). It is accepted that an isolated cavity grows and then two or more

isolated cavities coalesce, so cavities develop. The large cavities are because of cavity growth and coalescence. It should be noted that the cavities were grown perpendicular to the tensile direction in the specimen deformed at 12 MPa. on the other hand, the cavities were developed parallel to the tensile direction in the specimen deformed at 8 MPa. Stringers of cavities parallel to the tensile direction with lengths up to $\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$ were formed in the specimen deformed to failure at 8 MPa (Fig. 5). Such stringers of cavities parallel to the tensile direction were not found for the specimen deformed to failure at 12 MPa. These results

(a) 8 MPa

(b) 12 MPa

Fig. 4 Longitudinal sections of polished specimens, (a) $\epsilon = 1.8$ at 8 MPa with 833 K and (b) $\epsilon = 1.3$ at 12 MPa with 833 K, the tensile axis is horizontal.

indicate that the level of stress affects the direction of cavity growth as well as the cavity volume for the composite. The development of the perpendicular cavities is likely responsible for a rapid decrease in the elongation to failure at the higher stresses of more than 11 MPa for the composite.

Fig. 5 Stringers of cavities parallel to the tensile direction with lengths up to $\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$ in the specimen deformed to failure at 8 MPa with 833 K, the tensile axis is horizontal.

Cavity growth mechanisms can be classified into two categories, diffusion-controlled-growth [13-17] and plasticity-controlled-growth [17,18]. In general, cavities are grown parallel to the tensile direction for plasticity-controlled-growth. For many superplastic metals [19-21], cavity stringers were formed parallel to the tensile direction. Chokshi and Langdon [22] showed that the cavity stringers were associated with the stringers of second phase particles. For the composite, the Si_3N_4 particulates were distributed reasonably homogeneously. The development of cavities parallel to the tensile direction at 8 MPa is likely attributed to plasticity-controlled-growth mechanism. However, the origin of the development of cavities perpendicular to the tensile direction at 12 MPa is not clear at present.

The cavity volume was investigated by density measurements. The variation in the cavity volume as a function of true strain at 8 and 12 MPa with 833 K is shown in Fig. 6, where the data of a superplastic 7475 alloy are superposed. The cavity volume increased with increasing strain. It is found that the cavity volume at 12 MPa was much larger than that at 8 MPa in the strain range investigated. Thus, the level of the cavity volume largely depended on the applied stress for the composite. It should be noted that the rates of an increase in the cavity volume for the composite were much lower than that for the superplastic 7475 Al. To date, it is accepted that grain boundary sliding plays an important role in superplastic flow. It is expected that high stress concentrations are caused at the interfaces by the sliding process and cavities develop excessively for metal matrix composites. Surprisingly, however, the results in Fig. 6 reveal that the rates of an increase in the cavity volume were low for the composite and that the cavity volume at 8 MPa for the composite was low at large strains (> 1), compared with the superplastic aluminum alloy.

Recently it was revealed that partial melting occurred at matrix/reinforcement interfaces for superplastic aluminum matrix composites [23], and furthermore it was shown that a maximum

Fig. 6 The variation in the cavity volume as a function of true strain at 8 and 12 MPa with 833 K for the Si₃N_{4p}/Al-Mg-Si composite, where the data of a superplastic 7475 alloy are superposed.

elongation was attained at the temperature close to the partial melting temperature in superplastic aluminum matrix composites [8,9,24-26]. These results indicate that a liquid phase plays a vital role in superplastic deformation. Mabuchi and Higashi [26] proposed an accommodation process by a liquid phase as a new concept for the accommodation processes for superplastic deformation mechanisms. If a liquid phase plays a vital role in superplastic deformation, cavitation behavior is expected to be affected by the presence of a liquid phase. In this investigation, the testing temperature of 833 K is slightly above the partial melting temperature of the composite (829 K), and there exists locally a liquid phase under a condition of 833 K. Therefore, the facts that the rates of an increase in the cavity volume were low and the cavity volume at 8 MPa was low at large strains for the composite may be related to the presence of a liquid phase.

CONCLUSION

- (1) Tensile tests have been carried out under a constant stress condition at 833 K for a fine-grained Si₃N_{4p}/Al-Mg-Si composite. The composite showed superplastic behavior at high strain rates ($\geq 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$).
- (2) Large elongations to failure of more than 400 % were attained in a stress range from 6 to 10 MPa, however, the elongation to failure decreased rapidly at higher stresses of more than 11 MPa.
- (3) Cavities were nucleated preferentially at the matrix/reinforcement interfaces.

- (4) Cavities were developed parallel to the tensile direction in the specimen at 8 MPa, on the other hand, cavities were developed perpendicular to the tensile direction in the specimen at 12 MPa. A rapid decrease in the elongation to failure at the higher stresses of more than 11 MPa is likely attributed to the development of the perpendicular cavities.
- (5) The cavity volume strongly depended on the applied stress.
- (6) The rates of an increase in the cavity volume for the composite were much lower than that for a superplastic 7475 Al. Furthermore the cavity volume at 8 MPa for the composite was low at large strains. These may be related to the presence of a liquid phase for the composite.

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